

SURVEY ON SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY PRACTICES AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT REQUIREMENTS IN ROMANIAN FIRMS

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Abstract

Purpose – the paper raises awareness on corporate social responsibility (CSR) and investigates the linkages between the company profile and their practices and the employee profile and their involvement.

Methodology/approach – the study has been performed by surveying 88 individuals working in Romanian firms. The linkages have been discovered using regression analysis.

Findings – the results explained the linkages and outlined the main CSR strategic objectives that companies should have and to raise awareness between employees.

Research limitations/implications – the study is limited by the respondents' opinions related to their knowledge.

Practical implications – this study provides an updated view on the CSR practices in Romanian firms. It discovers any linkage between women integration programs after a career break, recent graduates' integration and environment protection programs and the company size and if the sector influences the adoption of environmental programs. It also analyzes if employees' gender and seniority level is linked to their involvement in CSR activities.

Originality/value – this study contributes towards the CSR view in Romania, enabling companies to adapt their programs using GRI (Global Reporting Initiative) standard with economic, social and ecological pillars and to raise awareness about the importance of such practices.

Key words: sustainable development, corporate social responsibility, globalization.

Introduction

Nowadays, globalization is an important concern. It has brought economic gains, such as international trade and services, improved transport, enabling movement of people and goods across the globe. In terms of culture and governance, globalization has led to transparency, providing greater access to press, telephones, computers and the Internet. On the other hand, globalization is perceived as creating threats to communities and environment, as it brings growth. Thus, it increases the gap between developed and undeveloped nations, it increases products consumption, it enables people migration and urbanization, ultimately leading to more emissions. Globalization processes are complex and to address the concerns, nations should have an integrated approach, combining all sustainability pillars (Martens and Raza, 2010).

To help companies report their sustainability performance, the GRI global knowledge database has been developed, providing reporting guidelines under the following pillars: ecological, social and economic. According to the report on GRI contribution towards the sustainable development goals (SDGs), GRI influences sustainable practices on the following themes: climate change, human rights, anti-corruption, market regulators, SMEs, trade and gender equality (GRI, 2020).

In the context of globalization, companies have now the opportunity and challenge to address sustainability themes at global and local level. Their impact on the community is significant and, to

ensure differentiation on the market, brand image and increased business profits, companies should adapt their sustainability practices. The global trend is to go beyond business as usual and to address global and local socially-responsible challenges.

Thus, firms should adapt their practices to ensure employee wellbeing, to contribute towards the community and to reduce their impact on the environment.

This paper addresses the concern for corporate social responsibility (CSR) and sustainable development (SD), identifies and analyzes the practices related to the requirements of sustainable development of companies operating in Romania.

Research problem

In Romanian scientific literature, the concepts have been introduced in 2011, demonstrating that the most common CSR actions are philanthropic, ecological and social (Ciulu, Onea and Tatarusanu, 2015).

A micro-level survey on conducted in 2014 demonstrated that CSR has three main benefits: improves company reputation, notoriety and organizational culture (Mitra and Borza, 2015).

The National Strategy for Promoting National Responsibility outlines that CSR has a legal, ethical and volunteer grounds, not only increasing profits (Ciulu, Onea and Tatarusanu, 2015).

On the other hand, CSR leads to a higher financial effort, time and logistics, and the efforts are not justified by the benefits obtained (Mitra and Borza, 2015).

A major threat to the CSR implementation in Romanian companies is the lack of knowledge and awareness, public policies and budgetary funds. An Ernst & Young research demonstrated that companies focus their efforts in educational (79%), social (68%), health (56%) and environmental programs (58%) (Popa, 2015).

However, a study on 80 Romanian companies demonstrated that, on average, companies are not concerned about implementing CSR programs (Gherghina and Vintila, 2016). According to another study, multinational companies' presence in Romania has increased the awareness in CSR activities (Dura and Imola, 2017).

Another study emphasized a clear connection between corporate CSR communication and reporting, whether it is a CSR report or a dedicated section on the annual or financial report (Iamandi, 2012).

Although there is plenty of literature on Romanian's CSR, there are some gaps on the market analysis investigating the relationships between the company profile, the employees' profile and socially-responsible practices.

Thus, this paper aims to provide an insight on the sustainable development practices in Romanian firms by conducting a survey among employees and by using regression to identify the links between company profile and their practices, to provide an overview of the firms in the context of globalization. This paper analyzes the sustainable practices in the Romanian firms, aims to outline the state and propose indications for the future.

Research methodology

The aim of this paper is to identify and analyze the correlations between the company profile and their sustainable practices.

The paper methodological approach consisted in designing a survey to interview contributing individuals and managers on their view on the CSR practices developed in the companies they work for. The data collection consisted on a questionnaire filled by 88 individuals from different sectors (IT, consumer-facing sector, energy, other) and sizes (large, medium, small companies).

To analyze their view on CSR practices developed by their companies, multiple choice questions have been addressed and the authors have applied linear or multiple regression and ANOVA methods using SPSS.

Linear regression is a method to predict the value of a variable (dependent) based on the value of another variable (independent or predictor). It has the following formula:

$$Y = a + bX$$

where X is the predictor variable, Y is the dependent variable, b is the slope of the line, and a is the intercept (Laerd Statistics, 2018).

The following variables have been used interpret the outcome of the linear regression:

- Pearson correlation – to measure the association between two variables
- R^2 - how much of the total variation in the dependent variable
- F and $Sig.$ - statistical significance of the regression model and $Sig.$ has to be less than 0.05 (Laerd Statistics, 2018).

Results and findings

The demographic structure of the sample is based on 35,2% of individuals working in other industries, 33% working in ICT (IT, telecommunications, professional services), 27,3% working in consumer-facing sectors (retail, food, tourism) and 4,5% working in the energy and infrastructure (extractives, transport, heavy manufacturing, power and utilities).

Mostly women have responded to the questionnaire, 76,1%, and 23,9% men. The majority had between 20 and 30 years old (69,3%), followed by 21,6% between 30 and 40 years old and 9,1% over 40 years old, the majority being contributing individuals (81,8%).

The study covered 39,8% individuals working in large enterprises (+499 employees), 38,6% in small enterprises (1-49 employees) and 21,6% in medium enterprises (50-499 employees).

The majority of the companies provide flexible working time for both women (71,6%) and recent graduates (53,4%). Recent graduates are also offered internships and junior programs (47,7%), job fairs (35,2%) and open doors programs (19,3%).

The most popular actions undertook by the companies for environment protection are: reducing their energy usage (56,8%) and their general waste (53,4%).

To discover some liaisons between the company profile and their sustainable practices, the authors have applied linear or multiple regression.

The following section presents the correlation analysis between the research variables.

A1: Correlation between company size and practices on supporting women after a career break.

According to a study, multinational companies are aware that CSR enhances the company's reputation and consolidates its employer's brand, which might engage employees and create a better organizational environment and culture (Obrad and Gherhes, 2018).

A good organizational culture implies sustaining inclusion, diversity and integrating women and recent graduates in the workforce. A study outlined that in United Kingdom, women after a career break wishing to enter the ICT workforce face challenges like the lack of flexi-time schemes or part-time work and are not trained properly (Panteli, 2013).

In Romania, the current survey revealed that the majority of the companies provide a flexible working time (71,6%), a work from home option (44,6%) and only 17% mentioned that they have programs to recruit women after a career break.

To discover if the company size influences practices on supporting women after a career break, authors performed linear regression.

There is a slight correlation between the variables (Pearson = 0.273). The company size accounts for only 7.4% of the variance in integrating women after a career break ($R^2 = 0.074$). As ANOVA shows, the F value is 6.907 and the statistical significance Sig. is 0.01, hence the predictor is significant.

A2: Correlation between company size and practices on integrating recent graduates in the workplace.

Integrating recent graduates into the workforce is beneficial for both parties: the right internship program enables graduates to practice their theory and the companies to provide a job for those skilled interns (Coco, 2000). Companies can integrate recent graduates into workforce through internships, apprenticeships, graduate programs and entry-level jobs. They can get in touch with students through job fairs and provide open doors programs, seminars on different subjects and company presentations to advertise their opportunities.

In Romania, this survey revealed that the majority of the companies provide a flexible working time (53,4%), followed by internships and junior programs (47,7%), participation to job fairs (35,2%) and work from home option (31,8%).

To discover if the company size influences practices on integrating recent graduates in the workplace, authors performed linear regression.

There is a slight correlation between the variables (Pearson = 0.204). The company size accounts for only 4.2% of the variance in graduate's integration programs ($R^2 = 0.042$). As ANOVA shows, the F value is 3.732 and the statistical significance Sig. is 0.05, hence the predictor is significant.

A3: Correlation between company size and practices on environmental protection.

A study performed in 2015 revealed that large companies developed environmental programs (Popa, 2015).

Reducing energy usage (56,8%) and general waste (53,4%) were the most common environmental protection approaches undertaken by Romanian companies.

To discover if the company size influences practices on environmental protection, authors performed linear regression.

There is a slight correlation between variables (Pearson = 0.206). The company size accounts for only 4.2% of the variance in environmental protection programs ($R^2 = 0.042$). As ANOVA shows, the F value is 3.801 and the statistical significance Sig. is 0.05, hence the predictor is significant.

A4: Correlation between company sector and the development of energy efficiency programs.

According to a study, the companies that developed CSR programs for the environment are in the energy and infrastructure sectors (Popa, 2015).

To discover if the company sector influences the development of energy efficiency programs, authors performed linear regression. Pearson correlation is 0, therefore there is no correlation between the company sector and environment protection programs. The ANOVA test reveals the statistical significance Sig. as 0.467, hence the predictor is not significant.

From 88 responses received, only one company activated in the energy and infrastructure sector, hence the results of this test are not concluding and a deeper study must be conducted.

A5: Correlation between the gender and seniority level and the employee's involvement in CSR programs.

A 2018 study on a multinational company in Romania demonstrated that more than half (56%) of the employees didn't participate on any kind of CSR activity, whereas 34% participated sometimes (Rosca, Badulescu and Bac, 2018).

Another study containing 84 surveys from Bihor County employees, revealed that their age didn't have any impact on their CSR actions (Badulescu, Badulescu, Saveanu and Hatos, 2018).

This current study performed on 88 individuals from different company sectors aims to understand if the employee's involvement in CSR programs are influenced by the gender and seniority level.

To discover the linkages, the authors performed a multiple regression, where the dependent variable is employee's involvement and the independent variables are: gender and seniority level (contributing individual or manager).

Pearson correlation is 0.012 for gender and 0.276 for job level, hence there is a slight correlation between the job level and employees' involvement. Taking as a set, the predictors account only for 7.6% of the variance in the employees' involvement in CSR activities ($R^2=0.076$).

The ANOVA and Coefficients analysis reveal that the regression model is significant ($\text{Sig.}=0.035$) and only the job level ($\text{Sig.}=0.010$) is a significant predictor.

Table 1. Summary of findings for this study

Company / Employee profile	Supporting women	Integrating graduates	Environmental protection	CSR involvement
Company size	Pearson = 0.273 $R^2 = 0.074$ F = 6.907 Sig. = 0.01	Pearson = 0.204 $R^2 = 0.042$ F = 3.732 Sig. = 0.05	Pearson = 0.206 $R^2 = 0.042$ F = 3.801 Sig. = 0.05	-
Company sector	-	-	Pearson = 0 Sig. = 0.467	-
Gender	-	-	-	Pearson = 0.012 Sig.=0.972
Seniority level	-	-	-	Pearson = 0.276 Sig.=0.010 Set: $R^2 = 0.076$ Sig.=0.035

By summing up the findings, these results explore the links between the company characteristics and their CSR practices, as well as the employee profile and their CSR involvement.

This study reveals that on average, companies provide one program to integrate women after a career break and two programs for recent graduates, the company size having a slight influence on these. The company sector doesn't influence company's environmental protection programs.

The seniority level (contributing individual or manager) influences the level of involvement in CSR activities, and looking at the survey results, managers are more active.

As strategic plan, to implement corporate social responsibility practices, companies can work with specialized agencies and create a CSR department under marketing or HR to be in charge with their implementation. Visibility on this practice is necessary for the employees to get involved. CSR practices enable companies to build a stronger organizational culture, an enhanced brand image and competitive advantage.

To encourage employees into CSR activities, companies should provide the grounds. They can organize team buildings for environmental and social clauses such as: planting trees, cleaning forests, donating money to a cause, teaching, training or providing successful career stories to young people or future high school graduates. To report their CSR activities, companies can use GRI guidelines on social, environmental and economic contributions.

Conclusions

This paper is grounded on several previous studies conducted in the Romanian market on the issues of correlation between CSR and relevant involvement in social initiatives. They suggested some connections between social responsibility communication and involvement in social initiatives, as well as the links between the CSR practices and the firm value.

This paper provided an up-to-date view on the CSR practices in Romanian firms, showing if there is a clear liaison between the company size or sector and sustainable practices and if the employees' gender and seniority level influence their involvement in CSR activities.

By knowing these liaisons, companies can adapt their practices in order to enhance their sustainable development strategies.

The limitations of current research emerge from the sample population, only 88 responses have been received from contributing individuals and managers from 3 major sectors (ICT, energy and infrastructure, consumer-facing goods), whereas the energy and infrastructure sector has been poorly represented.

As future research avenues, authors purpose is to extend the research sample and to provide more links between the company's characteristics and their social responsibility and sustainable development involvement.

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